

CZU: 374.71

CONCEPTUAL AND METHODOLOGICAL FRAMEWORK OF IDENTIFYING ADULT'S LEARNING AND EDUCATION NEEDS

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This article addresses the issue of identifying the learning and education needs of adults, primarily non-formal education. Different concepts and models are analyzed to identify the learning and education needs of adults. A concept is grounded and a methodology is developed in this regard. The factors that generate the learning and education needs of adults are described in detail: external factors – national educational policies, institutional educational policies, educational reform projects, etc.; internal factors – the need for compensation, recapitulation, complementary knowledge, the need for retraining, the need to realize one's own interests and options, the need to capitalize on free time, etc. The emphasis is on establishing the tools for diagnosing needs, on forms and methods to carry out this process. At the same time, the way of obtaining and interpreting the data is argued. The proposed concept opens new perspectives for the development of formal and non-formal adult education and, first of all, of diversifying adult continuing education programs.

Keywords: *learning needs, adult's education, formal education, non-formal education, needs assessment/self-assessment, lifelong training/development, andragogy, training domains, motivational factors.*

CADRUL CONCEPTUAL ȘI METODOLOGIC AL IDENTIFICĂRII NEVOILOR DE ÎNVĂȚARE ȘI EDUCAȚIE A ADULȚILOR

În articolul dat se abordează problema identificării nevoilor de învățare și educație a adulților, în primul rând, a educației nonformale. Se analizează diferite concepte și modele de identificare a nevoilor de învățare și educație a adulților. Se fundamentează o concepție și se elaborează o metodologie în acest sens. Pe larg se descriu factorii ce generează nevoile de învățare și educație a adulților: *factorii externi* – politici educaționale naționale, politici educaționale instituționale, proiecte de reforme în educație etc.; *factorii interni* – necesitatea de compensare, recapitulare, complementare a cunoștințelor, necesitatea de recalificare, necesitatea de a realiza interesele și opțiunile proprii, necesitatea de a valorifica timpul liber etc. Accentul se pune pe stabilirea instrumentarului de diagnosticare a nevoilor, pe forme și metode de realizare a acestui proces. Totodată, se argumentează modul de obținere și interpretare a datelor. Conceptul propus deschide noi perspective de dezvoltare a educației formale și nonformale a adulților și, în primu rând, de diversificare a programelor de formare continuă a adulților.

Cuvinte-cheie: *nevoi de învățare, educația adulților, educație formală, educație nonformală, evaluarea/ autoevaluarea nevoilor, formare/ dezvoltare continuă, andragogie, domenii de formare, factori motivaționali.*

Introduction

Adults' education has as its subject and object the individuals in a concrete phase of the life cycle, characterized by autonomy, independence and experience. Adults' education targets them in their many states, roles, generated by contexts, needs and responsibilities, which they assume or must assume. Adults are constantly obliged to make decisions, to propose solutions, to develop action strategies and, above all, to take action. Adults' education involves the formation of personality, primarily through self-training and self-education, which requires the ability to work independently and decide independently. Self-cognition, creative spirit, self-control are traits of the adult that have their origin (diligence) at this stage of life.

Adults' education, on the one hand, is a process that contributes to the change and development of society, on the other hand, it is a process determined by societal changes with priority given to those on the labor market. Through adults' education, the necessary thinking and behavior techniques are transmitted to the adult in different professional and non-professional situations.

Adults' education opens up new opportunities for solving life problems, for acquiring new knowledge towards the world, towards themselves.

The concept of "learning to learn" remains a dominant one at this age as well: the acquisition and valorization of the means of fast and efficient search for information, the ability to verify information and its use in the educational process, but also in professional activity; the ability to work in a team and individually.

In this context, the issue of identifying adults' learning needs is becoming a priority. Namely, the cognition and awareness of one's own learning needs guides the adult to choose one or another type of education. As a rule, most adults do not have mechanisms for identifying their own learning needs. Very often adults make decisions to attend one or another educational activity, intuitively or strictly contextual.

Concept of “Need” Regarding Adults’ Learning and Education

The explanatory dictionary of the Romanian language [2] explains the notion of “need” as what is required, must be done; necessity, demand, requirement; issue, situation, business whose solution has an urgent, pressing character. The need reflects the existence of a problem that requires intervention, a problem that must be treated/solved, an impediment in carrying out a process, a professional/non-professional activity. “Need” can also be explained from the perspective of motivational theory and self-actualization by Abraham Maslow, who proposed a hierarchy of needs, ranging from primary biological needs to complex psychological motivations, such as the need to self-actualize and valorize on one’s own potential.

Fig.1. Pyramid of Necessities – by A.Maslow [3; 4, p.122].

Addressing needs according to A. Maslow is a matter of priority; the needs of one level should be at least partially met, so that those at the next level can manifest themselves and become important motivators of the individual’s actions.

This approach has specific implications for the education system and, in particular, for the adults’ learning and education system. If in the process of educating students their higher needs, such as cognition and understanding, cannot be activated, and if the lower needs are not met in the hierarchy of needs, then, in the process of learning and education for adults, this condition largely disappears, because the basic needs of adults are met. In this sense, higher needs (of development, the adult’s desire to be successful, to know, to valorize on their skills and cognitive, aesthetic and self-actualization skills) are dominant in adults’ learning and education. Without resorting to criticism of A.Maslow’s theory, it is certain that there are many individual differences in the order of occurrence and satisfaction of needs.

However, the methodology proposed by A.Maslow remains an effective mechanism for organizing the learning environment in a way that stimulates the active participation of adults in the learning process, satisfying their needs.

In order to establish the mechanisms for identifying the learning and education needs of adults, it is necessary to start from typological groups of adults: *adults who need lifelong vocational training* (qualification, requalification, improvement, recognition) and *adults who need personal training* (of general culture).

Further, we present the classification of learning and education needs on the professional dimension according to the typological groups of adults.

Fig.2. Learning and Education Needs in Relation to Typological Categories of Adults.

Otherwise, the framework of adults' learning and education needs from the perspective of their personal development (general culture) is presented.

On the one hand, identifying the learning and educational needs of this group of people is a simple procedure, because the basic criteria are the skills and abilities formed and realized by adults and that they want to develop (here appears the problem *where?* and *how?*). On the other hand, identifying the learning and educational needs of this group of people is a complicated procedure (practically not addressed in theory and practice), if the adults do not have a predisposition (attitude) for one or another field/activity profile, but they want to participate in non-professional training.

It should be noted that there are at least two aspects of identifying the learning and education needs of adults. The *first aspect* is related to external factors: experts, counselors, managers apply a respective tool in identifying the learning and education needs of specific groups of adults. The *second aspect* is related to the inner factor: the adult can establish his/her own learning needs, having the respective tools at his/her disposal, or he/she identifies his/her own needs strictly intuitively, contextually, motivatively.

Clearly establishing the learning and education needs of adults is a condition and a key factor in ensuring the quality of education and meeting these needs.

It should be noted that managing the process of identifying the learning and education needs of adults is a complex and complicated act.

In order to establish a methodology and tools for identifying the learning and education needs of adults, it is of interest and the vertical approach to needs, first of all, with reference to formal and non-formal lifelong vocational training. In this context, *four categories of needs* are established:

1. The needs that are generated by the educational policies, by the possible changes in the education system at the national level;
2. The needs that are generated by the regional/district policies, the possible changes in the education at the district level;
3. Institutional needs related to possible changes generated by educational institutions;
4. Individual/ personal needs generated by problems, gaps, weaknesses on the professional dimension or generated by the desire to obtain a teaching degree or higher performance.

Methodology and Tools for Identifying Learning and Education Needs of Adults

The diversity of adults' target groups, the diversity of adult education areas and profiles, the diversity of adults' learning and education needs create major obstacles in developing a methodology and tools for identifying adults' learning and education needs. In what follows, we will try to base a core methodology on identifying the learning and education needs of adults that can be modified, adapted in relation to one context or another.

Therefore, the methodology for identifying the learning and education needs of adults is a system of principles, methods, tools for establishing and analyzing needs, structuring needs, assessing needs, processing the data obtained and predicting the satisfaction of these needs.

The proposed methodology focuses mainly on the formal and non-formal lifelong vocational training of adults. In this context, the need is the discrepancy between the current stage of professional development of one or more persons and the desired (possibly achievable) stage. The *need* reflects the existence of a problem concerning a person or a group of persons, generated, inclusively, by national, district or institutional educational policies.

The methodology for identifying the learning and education needs of adults focuses on the following **principles** and **provisions**:

- The diagnosis of learning and education needs of adults must be systematic;
- The diagnosis of individual learning and education needs of adults must be autonomous and secure;
- The diagnosis of needs of a group of people must be transparent to make the right decisions;
- The analysis of learning and education needs of diagnosed adults must be cyclical, with the involvement of stakeholders to establish their priorities and how to meet them;
- The analysis of sources that directly and indirectly generate the emergence of needs for adults' learning and education: educational policy documents, curricular documents, strategies and programs for institutional development, etc.;
- The identification of mechanisms/tools for identifying adults' learning and education needs in relation to individual, institutional, regional and national options.

Therefore, the needs for lifelong vocational training/development are identified at different levels: individual, institutional, district, national. Through the analysis of these needs, individual, institutional, district, national projects for lifelong vocational development are elaborated.

It should be mentioned that the identification of needs of adults' lifelong vocational development within different professional fields has its own specificity, determined by the particularities of these fields: structure, types of activities, etc.

In this context, the lifelong vocational development needs of adults can be classified as follows (*see* Table 1).

Table 1

Classification of Adults' Lifelong Education Needs

Category of Needs			
At Individual Level	At Institutional Level (in addition to individual ones)	At Regional/ District Level (in addition to individual and institutional ones)	At National/ System Level
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • of conceptualization; • of designing; • of implementation; • of teaching; • of evaluation/ monitoring; • of communication; • of networking; • of research; • etc. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • of creating new institutional experiences; • of valorizing institutional policies; • of promoting institution's specifics/ educational orientations; • of group activity; • of communication with parents; • of activity in community; • of activity in institutional projects; • etc. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • of promote district policies; • of promoting teachers' experiences at district level; • etc. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • of applying national educational policies; • of applying changes at system level; • of participation in national projects; • of obtaining teaching/ managerial degrees; • etc.

It is important to establish the modalities and structures involved in meeting these needs. In this sense, the determinants become the categories of needs (*see* Table 2).

Table 2

Modalities and Structures Involved in Meeting Adults' Lifelong Vocational Training Needs*

Category of Needs			
At Individual Level	At Institutional Level	At Regional/ District Level	At National/ System Level
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • self-training; • institutional seminars; • individual projects; • etc. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • institutional seminars; • round tables; • exchange of experiences; • presentation of open lessons; • etc. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • district seminars; • round tables; • district conferences; • district thematic conferences; • etc. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • long-term and short-term lifelong vocational training courses (carried out by Lifelong Education Centers); • national conferences; • specialized lifelong training courses; • etc.

Another approach to identifying the learning and education needs of adults is related to their personal development/ general culture development. In this regard, we highlight three important aspects:

1. The adult identifies his/her personal development needs in relation to the skills, interests, abilities already formed and acknowledged. The choice for one or another educational activity the adult chooses consciously, in order to satisfy these interests in elderly age as well. Usually, this process is spontaneous and unmanaged from the outside.
2. The adult does not have concrete predispositions for one or another learning activity in a certain field, but he/she wants to participate in different training activities. In this case, the adult uses acquaintances, Internet sources, etc. The analysis of different options, *for example*, can arouse interest for choreographic, musical, sports, etc. activities. In this case, we can talk about interests and hidden options.
3. Service providers in the field of adults' personal development come with offers for adults, using different forms: conversations, advertising of different activities, involvement of adults in pre-program activities, etc.

Tools for Identifying/Assessing Learning and Education Needs of Adults

Different tools are used to identify/self-assess the learning and education needs of adults and, first of all, the needs of lifelong vocational training, each one having both advantages and disadvantages.

The determination of respective tools also depends on the category, the typology of the adults, the way of manifesting the need (*see* Table 3).

Table 3

Instruments for Identifying Learning and Education Needs of Adults in Relation to Their Category (regarding teachers)

Categoria nevoilor			
At Individual Level	At Institutional Level	At Regional/District Level	At National/ System Level
Self-assessment based on: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • questionnaire; • needs assessment sheet; • opinion of colleagues, methodologists; • ... 	Evaluation by administration: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • questionnaires; • interview; • evaluation form; • observation; • brainstorming; • case study; • ... 	Assessment by education department: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • questionnaires; • interview; • focus group; • evaluation form; • brainstorming; • case study; • ... 	Evaluation by MER [Ministry of Education and Research] or lifelong training institutions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • focus group; • questionnaires at national level; • analytical study; • study of policy documents; • study of reform documents; • ...

* Regardless of the structure of lifelong vocational training needs, teachers/managers may choose one or another lifelong vocational training program (subject) in relation to the individual, district or national needs proposed on the market of educational services.

It should be noted that the proposed instrument is mainly focused on establishing the learning and education needs of adults in the field of lifelong vocational training of managers and teachers. However, this tool can be adapted to other professional fields, as well as to the lifelong non-professional training of adults (professional development).

Therefore, as tools for identifying and assessing/self-assessing the learning and education needs of adults, we present the following:

The questionnaire is one of the most frequently applied primary tools. The questionnaire is a document that contains a set of questions that must be answered by the person completing it. The questionnaire may include different types of questions: grid questions, open-ended questions, etc., but should not take more than 15-30 minutes to complete. The questionnaire can be sent for completion directly or indirectly. The tool offers *advantages*: the person can complete the questionnaire at his/her own pace, the results of the questionnaire can be kept confidential; but also *disadvantages*: the respondent does not always have enough experience to make an objective assessment and, therefore, the results are more suitable for quantitative studies.

The interview, another tool/method, requires not only the development of a set of questions (sometimes this is called a *protocol*), but also the preparation of people who will conduct the interview. Open-ended questions are usually used in the interview, but may contain other types of questions. The interview offers the possibility of a qualitative assessment of the situation, but requires more time and more care in data processing. The interview requires careful preparation and the establishment of a constructive relationship between both actors in the process.

The *focus group* is also an assessment tool and method, which, like those described above, is based on a set of questions prepared in advance. The focus-group interview is conducted in person by a moderator, who asks questions to the group. The moderator must know in detail the aspects of the area discussed in the focus group, must be able to create a risk-free environment for participants, provide the necessary time for each participant, and channel the discussion, so as not to deviate from the topics set out in the set questions prepared in advance. The focus group provides a broader picture of the real situation, but, at the same time, the opinions of some participants may be influenced by the opinions of the majority, people may be reluctant to talk openly about certain topics, for fear of consequences.

At the base of each open tool is a set of questions. Each tool can provide a new perspective on the object under investigation, so these tools are not excluded, but can be used as complementary tools for a deeper study of the situation.

Regardless of the methods and tools selected in each individual case, it is important to obtain clear evidence to substantiate, justify the findings and formulate valid conclusions.

Adults' Learning and Education Needs Assessment Sheet*

The application of *Adults' Learning and Education Needs Assessment Sheet* provides for a number of actions.

Understanding the essence and importance of the evaluation process and motivating institutions and adults to participate in that investigation is the first in a series of actions. Needs analysis and assessment of adults' performance is one of the key elements in the development, in this case, of the educational institution, as it identifies areas for investment to help adults improve their work and increase the institution's performance. The process of analyzing and assessing the needs of lifelong vocational training can be seen as a tool to support decision-making regarding the organization of lifelong vocational training activities at different levels.

The tool will be applied by an operator (and individually). The operator can be the trainer of the lifelong vocational training institution, the methodologist from the District Education Directorate or the teacher/administrator responsible for human resources management in the educational institution. The operator will give clear instructions on the purpose and manner of completion until distributing the *Sheet*. He/she will insist that participants read the presentation page of the tool. The operator will emphasize the importance of notifying the interpretation of the meaning levels A, B, C, D and the score (1-5). It should be noted that each question requires only one answer. An issue that needs to be emphasized, then respected, is that of maintaining confi-

* Adapted from Chicu, V., Solovei, R., Hadîrcă, M., Paniș, A., Cara, A. Lifelong training of teachers in the context of learner-centered education (pp.15-40).

dentiality, so those evaluated may be reluctant to complete the *Sheet* honestly. By presenting the *Sheet* and providing clear instructions on how to complete them, we encourage you to complete and understand the tool.

In general, the operator's task is to:

- present and emphasize the relevance of the *Sheet* for the evaluated one, for the educational institution and for the institutions of lifelong vocational training;
- ensure the confidentiality of information given by the evaluated person;
- provide the necessary and sufficient explanations regarding the way of completing the *Sheet*;
- distribute the *Sheet*;
- collect the completed *Sheets*.

Those evaluated, who will use the *Sheet* for the purpose of self-assessment, identification of the needs of lifelong vocational training and elaboration of the individual plan of professional development will read carefully and will follow the instructions [1, p.18-20].

The Needs Assessment/Self-Assessment Sheet, in this case, of lifelong training of teachers can serve as a basis for establishing the educational offer of the institutions providing lifelong vocational training services, for the District Directorates of Education and for the educational institution to organize activities of lifelong training in relation to the identified needs, but also for the identification of one's own needs for lifelong professional development and the elaboration of the individual plan of professional self-training or choice of one or another offer.

Below we present a possible structure of the *Needs Assessment/Self-Assessment Sheet for Lifelong Vocational Training*, in this case, of teachers.

As mentioned, the *Sheet* is structured by areas of competences, reflected in professional standards:

- A. Cognition/Understanding;
- B. Awareness/Acceptance;
- C. Application/Valorization;
- D. Establishment/Resultiveness.

The logic of building the boxes is subject to the cause-effect connection: **if** I know and understand (level A), **if** I accept (level B) and apply (level C), **then** I find the results (level D). The mastery of each level will be appreciated by using a rating scale from 1 to 5.

The 5 points have the following meanings:

- 5 – excellent level;
- 4 – good level, describes your strengths and issues that could be improved;
- 3 – adequate level: strengths are more numerous than weaknesses;
- 2 – below average level: strengths are less numerous than weaknesses;
- 1 – unsatisfactory level: requires intervention.

The interpretation of meaning for each of 4 levels: A, B, C, D – is represented in Table 4.

Table 4

Interpretation of meaning for each of 4 levels: A, B, C, D

	1	2	3	4	5
A	You are not informed about the topic raised, do not use the terms.				You are well-documented, you can give a talk on the topic.
B	You do not agree with the statement, you have arguments against the statement.				You accept and agree with the statement, you have arguments and you can argue.
C	You do not practice other actions and activities, as a rule.				You systematically apply the full range of actions and activities listed.
D	You did not find the results described.				You systematically certify the results described.

Only one answer (one number) is circled for each statement!

Below we present, as an example, the structuring of *Sheet* on the dimension of competence *Didactic design*.

Table 5

Competence Domain: Didactic Design

Teacher:

1A	I know the principles that determine the peculiarities of didactic design from the curricular perspective.	1	2	3	4	5
1B	I formulate systems of arguments to demonstrate the topicality, importance and effects of respecting the principles of didactic design from the curricular perspective.	1	2	3	4	5
1C	I develop didactic projects respecting (i) <i>the principle of individuality</i> that ensures the development of individuality of the learner's personality and its manifestation as a subject of own learning; (ii) <i>the principle of choice</i> that ensures the right and development of the learner's ability to participate in decision-making regarding own learning objectives, contents, forms, methods and means of learning; (iii) <i>the principle of creativity and success</i> that contributes to the formation of positive self-conception, to the development of capacity for self-motivation; (iv) <i>the principle of trust and support</i> that stimulates the learner's activity oriented towards self-evaluation, edification and self-improvement.	1	2	3	4	5
1D	I ensure the obtaining from the learner of relevant information (the learner's interests, the motivation for learning, the style and the way of learning, the types of dominant intelligences, etc.) and their valorization in the didactic design of long and short duration.	1	2	3	4	5
2A	I know how to formulate the aims of learning in terms of performance in an interactive, individualized and differentiated context.	1	2	3	4	5
2B	I argue that the teacher must motivate and develop the learner's ability to establish the expected results of activities.	1	2	3	4	5
2C	I formulate the learning activities starting from the short-term and long-term expectations of each learner from the curricular requirements and from the competence of learners to concretize the learning outcomes.	1	2	3	4	5
2D	I ensure the creation of an educational environment and learning situations conducive to learner's co-interest/motivation and the development of competence to establish the expected results from the activity.	1	2	3	4	5
3A	I know ways to build teaching strategies so that they ensure academic performance and contribute to the development of the subject quality of each student.	1	2	3	4	5
3B	I argue the need and feasibility of building bivalent teaching strategies: aimed at achieving academic performance and developing the learner's subject quality.	1	2	3	4	5
3C	They build relevant teaching strategies for: valorizing on the potential of each learner, developing self-motivation for learning, taking responsibility for own learning, taking responsibility for one's own learning, monitoring the learning process, developing metacognitive and self-assessment skills and achieving academic performance.	1	2	3	4	5
3D	In the elaborated projects, I obtain didactic strategies that offer each child, in the learning process, the opportunity to carry out task systems with different levels of complexity, to manifest and be actively and responsibly involved, individually and as part of a team or of a group in academic and social contexts.	1	2	3	4	5

4A	I know the importance of identifying and using varied and innovative teaching resources during activities that facilitate cooperative learning, individualized and differentiated learning.				
	1	2	3	4	5
4B	I argue the need to design in the didactic approach the modern, current resources, which ensure the adequacy of content to the educational needs of each student and of the groups of students as a whole.				
	1	2	3	4	5
4C	I valorize in the didactic project the formative potential of informational, human resources and of the new and traditional materials that facilitate the learning of each learner.				
	1	2	3	4	5
4D	I ensure, through the relevance and adequacy of the capitalized resources, the creation of motivating learning situations for learners and the achievement of the expected results.				
	1	2	3	4	5
5A	I possess the information needed to turn the contents of training into meaningful content for learners.				
	1	2	3	4	5
5B	I argue the need and possibility to identify and emphasize the theoretical and practical utility for learners of each content topic included in the curriculum.				
	1	2	3	4	5
5C	I design the ways to motivate and involve learners in the study and application in various and significant contexts of content topics, the integration of each topic in the general structure of the study discipline; building logical connections of the subject studied in an interdisciplinary context.				
	1	2	3	4	5
5D	I obtain didactic projects that ensure the motivation of learners for the study of each content subject; understanding the role and place of the content studied in own skills system; acknowledgement of the new information's value and development of skills to use it in concrete contexts.				
	1	2	3	4	5
6A	I know the normative and methodological framework of curriculum design at the decision of institution.				
	1	2	3	4	5
6B	I argue the need to diversify the educational offer to meet the interests and educational needs of the learner, the institution and the community.				
	1	2	3	4	5
6C	I apply tools to identify educational interests and needs and develop a curriculum for that activity together with learners.				
	1	2	3	4	5
6D	I note the active involvement of educators in making decisions regarding the form of organization, contents, ways of organizing activities and in establishing the expected results of this study.				
	1	2	3	4	5

According to this model, the *Sheet* can be structured on other areas of competences: organizing the educational process, evaluation of learning outcomes, didactic communication, class management, etc.

Table 6

Synoptic Table* [1, p.36]

	A	B	C	D	Score Amount	Average Score
1						
2						
3						
4						
5						
6						
Subtotal I						Subtotal I : 6 = P

* The synoptic table includes the results of assessing all areas of competences included in the *Assessment Sheet*.

The purpose of data analysis and interpretation is to identify the nature of problems the teacher faces regarding, in this case, the didactic design and the specific actions to solve those problems. Thus, the integral process will consist of the following:

- identifying the problems faced by teachers;
- establishing the essence of identified problems;
- prioritizing the identified problems;
- establishing the objectives of lifelong vocational training;
- identifying possible solutions and selecting the relevant ones in the concrete context;
- designing the actions of lifelong vocational training and self-training in order to satisfy the needs of lifelong vocational training of teachers.

The identification of problems faced by the teachers will be made on the basis of the completed *Synoptic Table*.

The sum of the total score obtained may vary. If less than a set number of points is accumulated, there is an urgent need to include the teacher in a process of lifelong vocational training (or self-training).

The average score calculated according to the formula indicated for each *subtotal* will indicate the more or less problematic area for the teacher. Thus, the value obtained after calculating the average score for each *subtotal* indicates, by comparison, the most problematic *domain* for the teacher. Domains, for example, are indicated by letters: D – design; O – organization; A – assessment; PD – professional development; PM – psychosocial and management; T – technical. The calculated average can vary between 4 and 20. The averages with a value between 8 and 12 indicate areas in which the teacher faces multiple problems, and this indicates the need for intervention at the level of lifelong vocational training.

The *subtotal* in each of the 4 columns A, B, C, D will indicate the nature of problems faced by the teacher. This can be achieved by summing the allocated points vertically. For example, for the *Design* field, add the figures indicated in Table 6 vertically in column A from row 1 to 6, and the result obtained will be entered on *subtotal I* line at the intersection with *column A*. The same will be done with columns B, C and D. Table 7 shows the levels that indicate the urgent need for lifelong vocational training intervention.

Table 7

**Quotas Denoting Urgent Need
of Lifelong Vocational Training Intervention (as an example)**

	A	B	C	D
Subtotal I <i>Design Competence</i>	12	12	12	12
Subtotal II <i>Organization Competence</i>	8	8	8	8
Subtotal III <i>Assessment Competence</i>	14	14	14	14
Subtotal IV <i>Professional Development Competence</i>	12	12	12	12
Subtotal V <i>Psychosocial and Management Competence</i>	10	10	10	10
Subtotal VI <i>Technical Competence</i>	2	2	2	2

The accumulation of amounts less than or equal to those indicated in Table 7 shows an unacceptable level of professional training of the teacher.

To identify the nature of problem faced by the teacher, we will compare the amounts obtained on the *subtotal* line in each of the VI areas. The comparison of amounts obtained on each of the columns A, B, C, D will be interpreted as follows:

- The lower amount in column A, compared to the amounts obtained in columns B, C, D, indicates the need for information regarding the aspects indicated in the descriptors in boxes. The teacher does not have enough information on the subject, he/she is to be documented to define the concepts and to explain the terms.

- The smaller amount in column B, compared to the amounts obtained in columns A, C, D, shows the lack of conviction that the theory, the targeted educational concept is functional and necessary. The concept/theory in question does not fit into the teacher's value system and he/she does not accept that concept/theory. For example, the teacher understands the *learner-subject of learning* concept, but shares the belief that the learner cannot/should not assume the role of subject in the learning process. The teacher's problem is the lack of credible and sufficient arguments for him/her to accept that concept.
- The lower amount in column C, compared to the amounts obtained in columns A, B, D, indicates that the teacher does not apply in his/her practice the tools, methods, forms, etc. indicated, it does not valorize practically the theoretical concepts. This may be due to lack of the skills of didactic transposition, of targeted aspects' valorization.
- The lower amount in column D, compared to the amounts obtained in columns A, B, C, indicates the lack of expected results. The teacher may know the theoretical aspects, apply them, but not get the desired results, or not know how to observe and see those results. The smaller amount in column D may indicate the need to analyze the level of application: the lack of desired results may be caused by distortions in the practical application of methods, tools, etc.

Taking into account the situations described above, particular cases will also be interpreted.

In order to reduce the subjectivity, to increase the objectivity and credibility of the process of assessing the needs of lifelong vocational training of teachers, the form can be completed by the teacher, colleagues of the teacher or representatives of the educational institution's administration who attended the activity and have sufficient data to analyze his/her activity. The analysis of data that characterizes the teacher's activity from three different perspectives can provide the necessary and sufficient information for the elaboration of the *Individual Professional Development Plans*, for the elaboration of the *Activity Plans of Methodical Departments* in the educational institution and for the elaboration of the continuous professional training offers, creation of the market for curricula in the system of teachers' lifelong vocational training. Teachers, based on the data obtained, will be able to choose the form of training for courses and topics for discussion in career management counseling classes with teachers from institutions competent in lifelong vocational training.

Institutions, based on generalized results, will include teacher training content in the institutional plan; they will be able to guide/monitor the teachers in the elaboration and completion of the individual plan of professional development, in the design and development of the educational activities.

The Directorates of Education, based on the generalized results, will be able to plan/ organize various forms of teacher training at the district level, will draw up the lists of teachers delegated to training courses.

Based on the *Assessment Sheet for Needs of Teachers' Lifelong Vocational Training*, the institutions, and also each individual, will be able to build their own complementary systems of investigation to ascertain the initial level of developing professional skills in the key of postmodern education [1, p.37-40].

Conclusions:*

Establishing a conceptual and methodological framework for identifying and assessing/self-assessing the learning and education needs of adults and, where appropriate, teachers' lifelong education is part of the modern paradigm of lifelong learning. The proposed approach can be adapted and applied in order to establish the formal and non-formal learning and education needs of adults in different fields and professional profiles.

Therefore, identifying the learning and education needs of adults, prioritizing these needs, is a frame of reference for ensuring the quality of formal and non-formal vocational training of adults.

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* It should be noted that the conceptual approach to identifying the learning and education needs of adults can serve as a mechanism for identifying the needs of young people and adults to obtain a qualification or requalification.

Note: The paper was carried out within the State Program *Conceptual, Methodological and Managerial Framework of Non-Formal Education in the Republic of Moldova*, number 20.80009.0807.23.

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Presented on 30.03.2022